

DATA CITATION TASK TEAM

Recommendations for a sustainable data citation service for CMIP

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Contents

Background	5
The CMIP6 Data Citation Service	5
Community feedback	5
The Data Citation Task Team	7
Aims and Objectives	7
Task Team Work and Recommendations	8
Identified options	8
Recommendations and decisions	12
Risks	17
Next Steps	17

Background

The World Climate Research Programme (WCRP)'s Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)'s Data Citation Service was provided by the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ) during CMIP6, and is part of the CMIP data infrastructure, which falls under the governance of the WCRP Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) Infrastructure Panel (WIP).

DKRZ is experienced in data citations but is currently unable to maintain a data citation infrastructure component for CMIP, which is integrated into the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF). The solution for CMIP6 and input4MIPs relied on a single person and is run on ageing software components¹. Coordination and communication are a significant burden on staff time and no professional software developer is available, limiting the ability to offer significant service consolidation in terms of scalability and performance and to evolve the service in sync with the changes ongoing in related infrastructure components like ESGF and the Controlled Vocabularies (CVs).

Looking forward to CMIP7, DKRZ is unable to continue to provide the citation service and expand it to further WCRP projects. Community engagement, including the recent CMIP6 Community Survey, has highlighted the importance of data citations for the CMIP datasets for data providers, their funders, and for data users within the CMIP community and downstream.

Further, under the WCRP [Earth System Modelling and Observations \(ESMO\) Strategic Plan & Governance 2022-2030](#) there is an objective 'Promotion and wider use of the file/data standardization and archive/dissemination infrastructure developed for CMIP across WCRP'. Therefore, there is clearly a continuing, and growing demand for the CMIP Data Citation Service.

The CMIP6 Data Citation Service

The data citation concept for CMIP6 was designed to work within the limited resources, a strict project timeline and the dependency on changes of the data dissemination infrastructure ESGF while meeting the need for CMIP6 data citation. The WGCM requested a citation reference for the evolving CMIP6 data disseminated through the ESGF in 2017 meeting the requirements of [Force 11's 'Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles'](#) and enabling data citation prior to long-term archival and in-time for IPCC AR6. Full details and information can be found on the [CMIP6 Data Citation and Long-Term Archival website](#) and in [Stockhouse and Lautenschlager \(2017\)](#).

Community feedback

There are two sources of community feedback for the Citation Service:

1. [CMIP6 Citation Service Survey Results \(0.1\)](#), Martina Stockhouse (2021), [Zenodo](#).
2. [CMIP6 Community Survey 2022](#), Eleanor O'Rourke (2023), [Zenodo](#).

¹ Only software curation required for a continuation of the service has been done since its development in 01/2017. Continuous automated monitoring is running and user questions are still answered but with a delayed response and limited to emergency treatment.

The Citation Service Survey was focused on data citation managers, rather than the wider CMIP community; however, the overall themes that emerged from both surveys were similar. The benefit, and importance of provision of DOIs to CMIP datasets was highlighted by respondents with the support from the data citation service being described as excellent.

The provision of data citation information was not mandatory and indeed completion of data citation information, as described in the [dedicated CMIP6 Guide](#), was neither checked nor enforced by the ESGF Node Managers. However, citation information covered 97–98% of the CMIP6 data during the project and 100% by the IPCC WGI AR6 data and paper submission deadline, emphasising the importance attached to data citation. While reminders from the citation service providers to the responsible citation service managers were required to keep this high coverage, their effectiveness further emphasises the importance attached to data citation. The DataCite infrastructure was also very reliable with only two glitches in four years causing delays in DOI registration but without impact on the citation service functionality.

Key areas identified for improvement, based on the surveys' feedback and the data citation service manager, are:

Data citation discovery for data users

Improved search functionality and usability within the ESGF should be targeted as users found it difficult and time consuming to navigate between the ESGF CoG and the CMIP6 Citation Search as a standalone component. Suggestions included an API to support machine accessible CMIP6 data citation information; this would be particularly beneficial for data users analysing large amounts of data² e.g., IPCC authors.

Data provision by CMIP6 participants

Data providers requested improved editing functionality for individual experiment data via the GUI, as for MIP data, and the ability to create a citation for experiments used in multiple MIPs.

Integration with other data infrastructure aspects

In both surveys, there were suggestions to integrate the citation information with other infrastructure aspects; however, opinions on the form and direction of this integration are diverse. Integration into documentation service (ES-Doc and errata services) or into the registration and data creation (CMOR) process were suggested. The need of reducing the number of services/platforms for extracting information on data was emphasized.

The most common request was to add citation and license information into NetCDF file headers. DOI or persistent URL can be included in NetCDF data header as they remain stable (requiring a long-term commitment of the citation partners to maintain these). The inclusion of the data reference in the NetCDF file header is not possible, as, citation information such as author lists change during a CMIP phase and thus will have to be maintained separately from the data creation process, as was the case in CMIP6.

² Such an API has been added to the CMIP6 Citation service (documentation: <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/cmip-api-docs/>; API: <http://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/ceraresearch/cerarest/cmip6search>) and has been used to provide the data citation overview table at https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/CMIP6_CVs/docs/CMIP6_source_id_experiment_citation.html

In both the survey and personal communications, the Obs4MIPs community have expressed interest in citations for their datasets; in earth observation many data providers register their own DOIs. As some CMIP data providers or ESGF data nodes have expressed the same interest in minting their own DOIs, this use case has to be supported by a future citation service. CORDEX was interested in utilizing ES-DOC but not the Citation Service for their CMIP5 downscaling. Among other WCRP projects serving data through ESGF, CORDEX would also be an obvious candidate for data citation rollout beyond CMIP.

The experience from CMIP6, both from provider and user viewpoints, suggests a redesign of the citation service would be beneficial for CMIP7, and certainly for potential wider rollout across the WCRP landscape.

The Data Citation Task Team

Due to the loss of an available citation service for CMIP7 and beyond, the CMIP Panel set up a Task Team to discuss and clarify the optimal approach to the data citation service in early 2023. This was one of several Task Teams that were established to support the definition and planning of CMIP7.

Aims and Objectives

The key aim of this Task Team was to develop the concept of a sustainable data citation service, which

- Can support CMIP7 and other WCRP projects and MIPs,
- Is better integrated into the CMIP infrastructure,
- Provides improved services for data providers and data users based on the CMIP survey results.
- Shares effort and costs among several DOI-providing institutions increasing resilience of the service.

To achieve this aim, the Task Team was set the following objectives:

1. Prioritise requirements for CMIP7 and potential wider activities.
2. Identify stakeholders.
3. Define a maximum of three options for a future citation service.
4. Develop concepts, specify required services, and estimate costs (financial and human resource) for all options.
5. Carry out stakeholder engagement to determine the preferred options.
6. Develop an appropriate governance structure and process for establishment.

The implementation should be discussed and coordinated by the governance board.

The data citation service should be transformed into a sustainable, scalable and better integrated service, which can be provided for projects upon request, and which meets provider and user needs.

The Data Citation Task Team was established by the CMIP Panel with Martina Stockhause (DKRZ) and Sasha Ames (LLNL) as co-leads. An [open call for Task Team membership](#) was launched on 24 August 2022 and was closed on 2 October 2022, which received nine applications from seven countries. Of these, five were from woman, and four were from men. The applications were reviewed according to the desired experience criteria, as laid out in the [Open Call text](#). In total, four members were invited to

join the Task Team (see Table 1). One additional member was invited to join to ensure the Task Team had an appropriate breadth of skills and experience.

Name	Affiliation	Role
Martina Stockhause	DKRZ	Co-lead
Sasha Ames	LLNL	Co-lead
Bryan Lawrence	NCAS/CEDA	Member
Yiling Liu	NCI	Member
Hsin-Chien Liang	NTU/AS-RCEC	Member
Graham Parton	CEDA	Member
Aparna Radhakrishnan	NOAA-GFDL/Princeton University	Member

Table 1: CMIP Data Citation Task Team membership

Following the presentation the Task Team’s recommendations to the CMIP Panel and WIP, the CMIP Panel decided the Task Team had successfully completed their objectives and made the decision to close the Task Team. This decision was made on 18 March 2024, at the in-person CMIP Panel and subsequent WGCM meeting.

Task Team Work and Recommendations

The Data Citation Task Team has discussed the future of a citation service for CMIP7 and beyond. A prioritization of the functionalities of such a service was carried out, which resulted in the description of two options – a minimal or desirable citation service. Further technical details of the service were also discussed, such as who should be responsible for the governance, how to federate the effort of software development and service maintenance, and to what extent the service should be integrated into other CMIP infrastructure components.

Identified options

The Task Team identified three options for a future citation service: ‘Do nothing’, ‘Minimal’, or ‘Desirable’.

The details of the functionalities of these options, including information on dependencies and use cases, are summarized in Table 2. Functionalities can be implemented step-by-step. Those functionalities required for the CMIP7 Fast Track are marked in bold.

		Functionality	Priority	Dependencies on other functionalities (all depend on essential functionalities)	Use Cases	
Minimal option	Essential functionalities	1.1	Long-term maintenance of DOI landing page (recommendation of DataCite: https://support.datacite.org/docs/landing-pages): provide full bibliographic citation, access to data, license and DOI displayed, and access to data in ESGF; DOI properly tagged in code for the page (schema.org standard)	Essential		
		1.2	Long term preservation of citation information	Essential		
		1.3	Curation of URL for DOI and metadata at DataCite	Essential		
		1.4	Data long-term preservation of core variables for core experiments (DECK + ScenarioMIP) or more	Essential		
		1.5	Support of full DataCite Metadata standard? or only of mandatory information? (http://schema.datacite.org/)	Essential		
	Provide information including usage of project resources	2.1	Gather citation information and reuse CV registration information supporting humans and machines	High		
		2.2	Change of citation information pre-DOI registration	High	2.1	
		2.3	Change of subset of citation information post-DOI registration	High	2.1	
	Find/Access information including integration in CMIP infrastructure	3.1	ESGF index: enabling machine access and reuse in other portals and automated processing	High	2.1	IPCC AR7 plans; secondary services
		3.2	Google (Dataset) Search: schema.org standard implementation into DOI landing page	High	2.1	
		3.3	CMIP web page documentation of data citations	High		
		3.4	CMIP citation API for accessing and filtering of citation information (in addition to DataCite's API)	High	2.1	IPCC AR7 plans

			Functionality	Priority	Dependencies on other functionalities (all depend on essential functionalities)	Use Cases
	Internal processing	3.5	ESGF portal display citation information alongside the data	High	2.1, 3.1	
		4.1	Reuse CMIP CV registration information for pre-population	High	2.1	IPCC AR7 plans
		4.2	Register DOIs	High		
	4.3	Update metadata at DataCite	High	2.1, 2.2, 2.3		
	Statistics/ documentation	5.1	Part of CMIP documentation for participants	High		
		5.2	Part of documentation for ESGF DN managers	High		
		5.3	Part of CMIP documentation for data users	High		
	Use cases/ workflows to support	5.4	Documentation in provider interface (in GUI or CV template or alike)	High	2.1	
		5.5	Data reuse metrics (references in papers)	High	8.2	
		6.1	Citation information created during data preparation	High	2.1	
6.2		Citation information maintained independent of data preparation or registration	High	2.1		
6.3	DOI registration at time of ESGF data publication (or shortly after)	High	2.1, 6.1, 6.2, 4.2			
Desirable option	Find/Access information including integration in CMIP infrastructure	7.1	download of citation information together with data download	Medium	2.1, 3.1	IPCC authors
		7.2	Include in NetCDF header: similar to furtherInfoUrl	Medium		
		7.3	Use a tracking ID to get to the citation	Medium	7.5, 8.1	IPCC AR7 plans
		7.4	Provide metadata on OAI server for harvesting	Medium		
		7.5	Connecting DOIs to PIDs in Handle Metadata	Medium	7.3, 8.1	IPCC AR7 plans

		Functionality	Priority	Dependencies on other functionalities (all depend on essential functionalities)	Use Cases	
	Internal processing	8.1	Add DOI information to Handle Metadata	Medium	7.3,7.5	IPCC AR7 plans
		8.2	Add and process new references accessed through Scholix	Medium	5.5	
		8.3	Monitoring of data availability/accessibility in ESGF for DOIs	Medium		
	Statistics/ documentation	9	DOI registration statistics	Medium	4.2	
	Use cases/ workflows to support	10	DOI registration when data collections are declared "complete"	Medium		
	Provide information including usage of project resources	11	prepopulate citation information (authors, title, orcid, contributors, RORs, funders, funderIDs, grants, references, etc.) based on template (avoid provision of same information several times)	Low	2.1	
Internal processing	12	DOI versioning when new datasets for existing DOI get published or are retracted	Low			
Statistics/ documentation	13	Metadata updates statistics	Low	4.3,2.2,2.3		

Table 2 Citation service functionalities required for the minimal and desirable options. Functionalities in bold are required to be implemented before the first data from the AR7 Fast Track is published. Other functionalities can be added at a later date.

Recommendations and decisions

Following the development of the three citation service options, the Task Team requested the CMIP Panel and WIP take forward the Task Team's recommendations. These recommendations were submitted as part of two separate decision requests – one to the CMIP Panel and one to the WIP. The CMIP Panel were requested to take forwards Recommendations 1 and 2, while the WIP was requested to take forward all five recommendations.

At the CMIP Panel meeting on 12 March 2024 at 20:00 UTC, the CMIP Panel approved the following recommendations from the Data Citation Task Team:

- i. The CMIP infrastructure should support citation of model data.
- ii. CMIP should aim for a citation service with the desired functionality defined by the Data Citation Task Team.

At the WIP meeting on 20 February 2024 at 15:00 UTC, the WIP approved the following recommendations:

- i. The CMIP infrastructure should support citation of model data.
- ii. The CMIP infrastructure should support a citation service with the desired functionality defined by the Data Citation Task Team.
- iii. The citation service should follow a dual federated approach of a technically-federated open software development and a geographically-federated service provision with geographic liaisons. Furthermore, the citation service should be well-integrated into the ESGF and the software development should aim for a joint development with the ESGF (see Table 3 for more details).
 - a. This recommendation was approved subject to the Task Team providing a resourcing plan. This was successfully submitted to the WIP and can be found in Table 4.

At the WIP meeting on 12 March 2024 at 15:00 UTC, the WIP approved a further two recommendations from the Data Citation Task Team:

- iv. The code development, implementation, and code maintenance of the citation service should be governed by the ESGF-XC and the WIP, or a liaison appointed by the WIP, should oversee the service's fitness for purpose.
- v. The WIP should address the issue of the citation service's funding only within its role and capacity as an expert advisory body, advocate and support funding proposals for a citation service, and, in collaboration with the ESGF XC, advise the ESGF-SC on the technical and resource (financial and human) requirements to support them in identifying and allocating funding support.

Further details on the five recommendations can be found below.

Recommendation 1 - The CMIP infrastructure should support the citation of model data

The CMIP6 citation service will not be continued by DKRZ for CMIP7, and no party has committed to take this on.

Data citation has become a common service: Publishers have integrated data references and data availability statements in their author guidelines; the importance of data is increasing; and

the recommended CC-BY license requires an acknowledgement which in research is commonly provided by citing.

Therefore, the first decision presented to the CMIP Panel and the WIP was if CMIP needs data citation and an infrastructure to provide this (see [Risks section](#) for details on risks of “Do Nothing”). The Task Team recommended a data citation component for CMIP.

Recommendation 2 - The data citation services should include the desired functionality

The effort for the ‘minimal’ and ‘desired’ functionalities is estimated as

- **Minimal Option:** The minimal option provides basic functionality. It requires ca. 1 FTE for a year of funding for the software development and some overhead for coordination across participants. A fraction of an FTE is required for long-term curation of the DOIs and maintenance of the landing page.
- **Desirable Option:** The desirable option extends the minimal option with further functionalities. It requires a considerable higher effort in development and integration with estimated costs of an FTE over approximately 1.5-2 years of funding for software development and service integration. Part of the functionality can be added after the Fast Track provision (see Table 2 for details). A fraction of an FTE is required for long-term curation of the DOIs and maintenance of the landing page.

Some of the desired functionality supports use cases that the IPCC utilises, as well as satisfying IPCC’s FAIR data guidelines.

Therefore, the Task Team recommended the WIP and CMIP Panel support the desired option, if funding is secured.

Recommendation 3 - Open-source software development as part of the ESGF collaborative development and geographically federation operations.

The two options for the service development, implementation and maintenance are: a) a single institution responsible for development, implementation and maintenance of the service (as it was for CMIP6) or b) a federated approach with options of a technical, an activity-related or a geographic federation.

The Task Team recommended to the WIP the outlined dual federating approach of:

- A federated software development as an open-source project, *and*
- A geographically federated citation service with geographic liaisons responsible for DOI minting and supporting data providers.

See Table 3 for advantages and disadvantages of the federation approach. Furthermore, the citation service should be well-integrated into the ESGF, and the software development should aim for a joint software design and implementation with the ESGF.

A summary of resources required at each stage of the project (development and implementation, management, and sustainment) has been included in Table 4. The total

resources estimated for managing or running the service for CMIP7 will be spread over the number of partners. The integration into the ESGF software stack is recommended, which requires the support of the ESGF software developers. The sustainability of the service including sufficient funding will become part of the ESGF governance.

Advantages and disadvantages of dual federation (combination of technical and geographical approach)	
Option description	Federate the development effort of software components by technical component. ESGF node liaisons/regional citation partners with DataCite Membership provide DOIs and contact points
Service	+ shared DOI costs + high resilience against leaving providers + same functionalities across activities - high dependency on partners providing components
Development	+ experts for component development - high coordination effort for software development related to a single partner approach
Support	- first level support layer directing requests - high coordination effort
Providers	+ use of federated-ly developed software together with institutional DOI registration /low development effort - institutions may have restrictions on providing DOIs for data stored elsewhere - moderate costs for DOI providers (though lower than if there was a single provider across CMIP)
Participants	+ clear point of contact
Users (tech. partners, citation users, ...)	- fragmented project-specific services and various contacts

Table 3 Advantages and disadvantages of recommended federation option. + indicates an advantage, - indicates a disadvantage.

	Resource requirements for minimal option	Resource requirements for desired option	Role of WIP – ensures citation service meets CMIP requirements within its role and capacity as an expert advisory body	Role of ESGF-XC – technical – assesses viability and makes recommendation to ESGF-SC
Development and implementation	~1 FTE across 1 year <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – concept development – implementation – DataCite membership 	1.5-2 FTE across 1.5-2 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – concept development – implementation – DataCite membership 	Oversees fitness for purpose of the service	– TT recommends the ESGF-XC coordinates the federated development and implementation
Management (running and providing the service)	~0.5 FTE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Service and software maintenance – User support – DataCite membership 	~0.6 FTE (due to increased service complexity) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Service and software maintenance – User support – DataCite membership 	– Checks in on problems, designates a member to check on solution progress	– TT recommends the ESGF-XC coordinates the federated service
Sustainment (after project close)	– <0.1 FTE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Continued DataCite membership – Curation of DOI, core metadata, and landing pages – No long-term licence fees for any software or services (e.g. Scholix) 	0.1 FTE (due to increased functionality of desired option) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Continued DataCite membership – Curation of DOI, core metadata, and landing pages – No long-term licence fees for any software or services (e.g. Scholix) 	– Ensures information remains available and accessible	– Coordination of continued funding streams with ESGF-SC sponsors

Table 4 Resource requirements and roles across the lifetime of the citation service

Recommendation 4 – ESGF-XC governing code development, implementation and maintenance and WIP, or a liaison appointed by the WIP, overseeing the service’s fitness for purpose

The two principal governing options are a) a separated governance of the citation service or b) the integration of the governance into an existing governance body with a representative for the citation service. As the citation service should be well-integrated into the ESGF (see [Recommendation 3](#) above), the Task Team recommended the integration of the data citation governance into the existing ESGF governance (ESGF-XC), because

- a) the separated governance requires considerable efforts to collaborate with CMIP infrastructure components such as ESGF, CMIP-CV, etc., and
- b) the desired integration into the ESGF can be best achieved by a representation of the data citation in the existing ESGF governing body.

During the citation service’s lifecycle, the roles of the WIP, the ESGF-XC, and the ESGF-SC will vary. The different roles have been clarified in Table 4. Additionally, the Task Team wrote out their expected lifecycle:

RECOMMENDED DATA CITATION GOVERNANCE

1. The Task Team provided a recommendation of the options, a preferred option based on expert opinion of Task Team members and identified the associated resource requirement.
2. The WIP should provide an expert technical oversight on whether the option/s are fit for purpose and if the resourcing plan is realistic.
3. The CMIP Panel has provided a decision on which option supports the scientific and service ambitions for AR7 Fast Track and CMIP7. The desirable option was chosen.
4. The ESGF-XC should review these recommendations, determine the associated implementation requirements within the ESGF and either:
 - a. Accept the recommendation and resource requirements (based on technical rather than funding grounds), and together with their own implementation requirements provide a recommendation to the ESGFSC;
 - or
 - b. Do not accept the recommendation from the CMIP Panel and WIP and the citation service is referred back to the WIP and CMIP Panel.
5. The ESGF-SC should review the chain of recommendations and (financial and human) resource requirements and, if they agree, determine if funding is available or may suggest mechanisms of accessing funding with support from the CMIP Panel and WIP.

Recommendation 5 - Support for resourcing

The Data Citation Task Team recommendations i to v (See [Page 9](#)) are subject to funding and partner commitments. Historically, partners interested in a service committed to provide the required resources to ESGF-SC or in case of the citation service to the WIP. This is the first case in which no resourcing is provided. This request was revised according to the clarification of roles and responsibilities of the CMIP and ESGF bodies.

Risks

The main risks for the implementation of the recommended and CMIP Panel/WIP-approved data citation for CMIP7, resulting in having no coordinated data citation for CMIP7, are:

1. Lack of funding,
 - a. Another risk for implementation and governance is the required support by the ESGF, as continued supported is only possible through continuous funding of the ESGF partners.
 - b. During CMIP7 resources of the geographic liaison institutions are required to mint DOIs and provide user support for their share of the CMIP participants, which is not currently funded.
2. Lack of interest in the development and implementation of the data citation.

On the other hand, there is risk associated with taking a “Do Nothing” option. The Task Team assumes this option would entail that each data provider will make use of their own means of data citation, e.g., institutional or organizational resources and practices for minting DOIs or define their own data collection granularities for DOIs. An integration of these various DOI approaches in the ESGF is technically possible but will become unfeasible with a growing number of special arrangements with individual DOI providers. Moreover, such an inconsistent citation process would lead to a potentially onerous experience for the data user.

Next Steps

The Data Citation Task Team has fulfilled its original objectives to develop options for a future CMIP data citation service and was closed during the CMIP Panel meeting in Hamburg on 18 March 2024. The co-leads continue to serve in the WIP in the role as data citation experts and will supervise the potential project or consortium implementing a data citation service for CMIP7.